

ISic1258

I.Sicily inscription 1258

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone (local)

Object

altar

(?)

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2009.10.06

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates**

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Taormina, Antiquarium del
Teatro Antico, inventory 8

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140746

1. ἀμφὶ παραστάσι ταῖσδε Σαράπιδος Ἔστῃαι ἀγνὸν
2. βωμὸν Βαρκαῖος Καρνεάδης ἔθετο,
3. Εὐκρίτου υἱός, ξεῖνε, ὁ νεωκόρος ἅ θ' ὁμόλεκτρος
4. Πυθιάς ἅ κείνου καὶ θυγάτηρ Ἔρασώ.
5. ἀνθ' ὧν, ὧ κραίνουσα Διὸς μεγαλαυχέας οἴκους,
6. θυμαρὴν βιοτᾶς ὄλβον ἔχοιεν ἀεὶ.
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

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Bibliography

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